

Supplementary material supporting the article “Uncertainties in estimating the effect of climate change on 100-year return value for significant wave height”

Kevin Ewans^{a,b}, Philip Jonathan^{c,d,*}

^a*MetOcean Research Ltd, New Plymouth 4310, New Zealand.*

^b*Department of Infrastructure Engineering, University of Melbourne, Melbourne, VIC 3010, Australia.*

^c*Department of Mathematics and Statistics, Lancaster University LA1 4YF, United Kingdom.*

^d*Shell Research Limited, London SE1 7NA, United Kingdom.*

Abstract

This document provides supporting information for the main article, and should be read in conjunction with that article. The information provided takes the form of figures illustrating the data and analysis conducted, and accompanying text. Please note:

- This document should be read in conjunction with the main article
- A copy of the main article can be found at ygraigarw.github.io/EwnJnt23C1mChn.pdf
- The structure of this document mirrors the sections and appendix of the main article; e.g. Section SM4 here contains supplementary material (SM) for Section 4 of the main text.

Note that for brevity, the term “GCM” is used generically to refer to the source of wave output for all CMIP5 and CMIP6 models (whereas of course the wave output for CMIP5 is from a WAVEWATCH-III wind-wave model, forced by winds from a GCM). For the purposes of the current work, we also treat the forcing scenarios “RCP4.5” (for CMIP5 models) and “SSP245” (CMIP6) as comparable, since they assume the same extent (4.5 Wm^{-1}) of radiative forcing achieved in 2100. We treat scenarios “RCP8.5” and “SSP585” as comparable since they both achieve 8.5 Wm^{-1} forcing by 2100. Hence for brevity, we sometimes refer to the “RCP4.5” or “RCP8.5” scenario for all GCMs, on the understanding that when applied to a CMIP6 model, we refer to the corresponding SSP scenario.

*Corresponding author philip.jonathan@shell.com

SM1. Introduction

There are no supporting figures for this section.

SM2. Data sources

Figure SM2.1: Time-series of peaks over threshold (POT, top row) and annual maxima (AM, bottom row) of H_S from the ACCESS CMIP5 GCM (available for “Historical”, “Middle” and “End” time periods) for forcing scenario RCP4.5, at the centre location EoM (left) and SoA (right) neighbourhoods.

Figure SM2.2: Time-series of POT (top row) and AM (bottom row) of H_S from the FIO-ESM CMIP6 GCM for forcing scenario SSP245 (RCP4.5), at the centre location EoM (left) and SoA (right) neighbourhoods, for the time period of the CMIP5 data. Note that the period of CMIP6 “historical” data extends back to 1850.

SM3. Extreme value analysis

Figure SM3.1: Typical illustration of the estimated variation of 100-year POT H_S with time for CMIP5 sample (available for “Historical”, “Middle” and “End” time periods) using non-stationary extreme value (EV) analysis. Each grey line corresponds to the trend of return value in time based on one sample from the MCMC chain generated. Thicker grey lines correspond to the estimated 2.5%, median and 95% levels at each time point. Underlying POT data in blue, and EV threshold exceedances in red. The data illustrated correspond to INMCM4 GCM, scenario RCP4.5, meridional transect EoM for EV threshold level NEP4.

Figure SM3.2: Typical illustration of the estimated variation of 100-year POT H_S with time for CMIP6 sample (available for a single long time interval nominally corresponding to years 301-450) using non-stationary EV analysis. Each grey line corresponds to the trend of return value in time based on one sample from the MCMC chain generated. Thicker grey lines correspond to the estimated 2.5%, median and 95% levels at each time point. Underlying POT data in blue, and EV threshold exceedances in red. The data illustrated correspond to 1% CO_2 scenario, zonal transect SoA for EV threshold level NEP4.

Figure SM3.3: Typical illustration of the estimated posterior density of 100-year POT H_S using non-stationary EV analysis, for the start (1979, blue) and end (2100, red) years. Line styles represent estimates for EV threshold levels NEP1-4. The data illustrated correspond to INMCM4 GCM, scenario RCP4.5, meridional transect EoM.

SM4. Exploratory data analysis

Figure SM4.1: Comparison of ordered values of AM H_S for the Historical, Middle and End time periods, for all CMIP5 GCMs, and the FIO-ESM CMIP6 GCM, for forcing scenario RCP4.5 (and SSP245, top row) and RCP8.5 (and SSP585, bottom row) at the centre location of the EoM neighbourhood. Left-hand panels give scatter plots for the Middle period on the Historical period; right-hand panels give the corresponding plots for the End period on the Historical period. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. General trends are similar to those for POT.

Figure SM4.2: Comparison of ordered values of AM H_S for the Historical, Middle and End time periods, for all CMIP5 GCMs, and the FIO-ESM CMIP6 GCM, for forcing scenario RCP4.5 (top row) and RCP8.5 (bottom row) at the centre location of the SoA neighbourhood. Left-hand panels give scatter plots for the Middle period on the Historical period; right-hand panels give the corresponding plots for the End period on the Historical period. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. General trends are similar to those for POT.

Comparing ordered 40 largest values of POT H_S from CMIP5 ACCESS GCM in different time periods on meridional and zonal transects EoM

Figure SM4.3: Comparison of the ordered 40 largest values of POT H_S for the Historical and Middle time periods, for the CMIP5 ACCESS GCM, and forcing scenarios RCP4.5 (blue) and RCP8.5 (red), and locations on the meridional transect EoM. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is little evidence for change in H_S in time.

Figure SM4.4: Comparison of the ordered 40 largest values of POT H_S for the Historical and Middle time periods, for the CMIP5 ACCESS GCM, and forcing scenarios RCP4.5 (blue) and RCP8.5 (red), and locations on the zonal transect EoM. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is little evidence for change in H_S in time.

Figure SM4.5: Comparison of the ordered 40 largest values of POT H_S for the Historical and End time periods, for the CMIP5 ACCESS GCM, and forcing scenarios RCP4.5 (blue) and RCP8.5 (red), and locations on the meridional transect EoM. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is some evidence for decreasing H_S in time, although the picture is mixed.

Figure SM4.6: Comparison of the ordered 40 largest values of POT H_S for the Historical and End time periods, for the CMIP5 ACCESS GCM, and forcing scenarios RCP4.5 (blue) and RCP8.5 (red), and locations on the zonal transect EoM. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is little evidence for change in H_S in time.

Comparing ordered 40 largest values of POT H_S from CMIP5 ACCESS GCM in different time periods on meridional and zonal transects SoA

Figure SM4.7: Comparison of the ordered 40 largest values of POT H_S for the Historical and Middle time periods, for the CMIP5 ACCESS GCM, and forcing scenarios RCP4.5 (blue) and RCP8.5 (red), and locations on the meridional transect SoA. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is general evidence for increasing H_S in time.

Figure SM4.8: Comparison of the ordered 40 largest values of POT H_S for the Historical and Middle time periods, for the CMIP5 ACCESS GCM, and forcing scenarios RCP4.5 (blue) and RCP8.5 (red), and locations on the zonal transect SoA. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is some evidence for increasing H_S in time.

Figure SM4.9: Comparison of the ordered 40 largest values of POT H_5 for the Historical and End time periods, for the CMIP5 ACCESS GCM, and forcing scenarios RCP4.5 (blue) and RCP8.5 (red), and locations on the meridional transect SoA. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is general evidence for increasing H_5 in time.

Figure SM4.10: Comparison of the ordered 40 largest values of POT H_S for the Historical and End time periods, for the CMIP5 ACCESS GCM, and forcing scenarios RCP4.5 (blue) and RCP8.5 (red), and locations on the zonal transect SoA. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is general evidence for increasing H_S in time, especially for the RCP8.5 scenario.

Comparison of the ordered 40 largest values of AM H_S from CMIP5 ACCESS GCM in different time periods on meridional and zonal transects EoM

Figure SM4.11: Comparison of the ordered 40 largest values of AM H_S for the Historical and Middle time periods, for the CMIP5 ACCESS GCM, and forcing scenarios RCP4.5 (blue) and RCP8.5 (red), and locations on the meridional transect EoM. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is little evidence for change in H_S in time.

Figure SM4.12: Comparison of the ordered 40 largest values of AM H_S for the Historical and Middle time periods, for the CMIP5 ACCESS GCM, and forcing scenarios RCP4.5 (blue) and RCP8.5 (red), and locations on the zonal transect EoM. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is little evidence for change in H_S in time.

Figure SM4.13: Comparison of the ordered 40 largest values of AM H_S for the Historical and End time periods, for the CMIP5 ACCESS GCM, and forcing scenarios RCP4.5 (blue) and RCP8.5 (red), and locations on the meridional transect EoM. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is little evidence for decreasing H_S in time.

Figure SM4.14: Comparison of the ordered 40 largest values of AM H_s for the Historical and End time periods, for the CMIP5 ACCESS GCM, and forcing scenarios RCP4.5 (blue) and RCP8.5 (red), and locations on the zonal transect EoM. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is little evidence for decreasing H_s in time

Comparing ordered 40 largest values of AM H_S from CMIP5 ACCESS GCM in different time periods on meridional and zonal transects SoA

Figure SM4.15: Comparison of the ordered 40 largest values of AM H_S for the Historical and Middle time periods, for the CMIP5 ACCESS GCM, and forcing scenarios RCP4.5 (blue) and RCP8.5 (red), and locations on the meridional transect SoA. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is general evidence for increasing H_S in time.

Figure SM4.16: Comparison of the ordered 40 largest values of AM H_S for the Historical and Middle time periods, for the CMIP5 ACCESS GCM, and forcing scenarios RCP4.5 (blue) and RCP8.5 (red), and locations on the zonal transect SoA. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is general evidence for increasing H_S in time.

Figure SM4.17: Comparison of the ordered 40 largest values of AM H_5 for the Historical and End time periods, for the CMIP5 ACCESS GCM, and forcing scenarios RCP4.5 (blue) and RCP8.5 (red), and locations on the meridional transect SoA. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is general evidence for increasing H_5 in time.

Figure SM4.18: Comparison of the ordered 40 largest values of POT H_S for the Historical and End time periods, for the CMIP5 ACCESS GCM, and forcing scenarios RCP4.5 (blue) and RCP8.5 (red), and locations on the zonal transect SoA. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is general evidence for increasing H_S in time, especially for the RCP8.5 scenario.

Comparing ordered 40 largest values of POT H_S from CMIP6 FIO-ESM GCM in different time periods on meridional and zonal transects EoM

Figure SM4.19: Comparison of the ordered 40 largest values of POT H_S for the Historical and Middle time periods, for the CMIP6 FIO-ESM GCM, and forcing scenarios SSP245 (blue) and SSP585 (red), and locations on the meridional transect EoM. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is little evidence for change in H_S in time. Note that full name of CMIP6 GCM is FIO-ESM v2.0.

Figure SM4.20: Comparison of the ordered 40 largest values of POT H_S for the Historical and Middle time periods, for the CMIP6 FIO-ESM GCM, and forcing scenarios SSP245 (blue) and SSP585 (red), and locations on the zonal transect EoM. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is little evidence for change in H_S in time. Note that full name of CMIP6 GCM is FIO-ESM v2.0.

Figure SM4.21: Comparison of the ordered 40 largest values of POT H_S for the Historical and End time periods, for the CMIP6 FIO-ESM GCM, and forcing scenarios SSP245 (blue) and SSP585 (red), and locations on the meridional transect EoM. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is some evidence for decreasing H_S in time, although the picture is mixed. Note that full name of CMIP6 GCM is FIO-ESM v2.0.

Figure SM4.22: Comparison of the ordered 40 largest values of POT H_S for the Historical and End time periods, for the CMIP6 FIO-ESM GCM, and forcing scenarios SSP245 (blue) and SSP585 (red), and locations on the zonal transect EoM. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is some evidence for decreasing H_S in time, although the picture is mixed. Note that full name of CMIP6 GCM is FIO-ESM v2.0.

Comparing ordered 40 largest values of POT H_S from CMIP6 FIO-ESM GCM in different time periods on meridional and zonal transects SoA

Figure SM4.23: Comparison of the ordered 40 largest values of POT H_S for the Historical and Middle time periods, for the CMIP6 FIO-ESM GCM, and forcing scenarios SSP245 (blue) and SSP585 (red), and locations on the meridional transect SoA. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is general evidence for increasing H_S in time. Note that full name of CMIP6 GCM is FIO-ESM v2.0.

Figure SM4.24: Comparison of the ordered 40 largest values of POT H_S for the Historical and Middle time periods, for the CMIP6 FIO-ESM GCM, and forcing scenarios SSP245 (blue) and SSP585 (red), and locations on the zonal transect SoA. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is some evidence for increasing H_S in time. Note that full name of CMIP6 GCM is FIO-ESM v2.0.

Figure SM4.25: Comparison of the ordered 40 largest values of POT H_S for the Historical and End time periods, for the CMIP6 FIO-ESM GCM, and forcing scenarios SSP245 (blue) and SSP585 (red), and locations on the meridional transect SoA. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is general evidence for increasing H_S in time. Note that full name of CMIP6 GCM is FIO-ESM v2.0.

Figure SM4.26: Comparison of the ordered 40 largest values of POT H_S for the Historical and End time periods, for the CMIP6 FIO-ESM GCM, and forcing scenarios SSP245 (blue) and SSP585 (red), and locations on the zonal transect SoA. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is general evidence for increasing H_S in time, especially for the RCP8.5 scenario. Note that full name of CMIP6 GCM is FIO-ESM v2.0.

Comparing ordered AM H_S from CMIP6 FIO-ESM GCM in different time periods on meridional and zonal transects EoM

Figure SM4.27: Comparison of the ordered AM H_S for the Historical and Middle time periods, for the CMIP6 FIO-ESM GCM, and forcing scenarios SSP245 (blue) and SSP585 (red), and locations on the meridional transect EoM. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is little evidence for change in H_S in time. Note that full name of CMIP6 GCM is FIO-ESM v2.0.

Figure SM4.28: Comparison of the ordered AM H_S for the Historical and Middle time periods, for the CMIP6 FIO-ESM GCM, and forcing scenarios SSP245 (blue) and SSP585 (red), and locations on the zonal transect EoM. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is little evidence for change in H_S in time. Note that full name of CMIP6 GCM is FIO-ESM v2.0.

Figure SM4.29: Scatter plots comparing the ordered AM H_S for the Historical and End time periods, for the CMIP6 FIO-ESM GCM, and forcing scenarios SSP245 (blue) and SSP585 (red), and locations on the meridional transect EoM. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is little evidence for change in H_S in time. Note that full name of CMIP6 GCM is FIO-ESM v2.0.

Figure SM4.30: Comparison of the ordered AM H_S for the Historical and End time periods, for the CMIP6 FIO-ESM GCM, and forcing scenarios SSP245 (blue) and SSP585 (red), and locations on the zonal transect EoM. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is little evidence for change in H_S in time. Note that full name of CMIP6 GCM is FIO-ESM v2.0.

Figure SM4.31: Comparison of the ordered AM H_S for the Historical and Middle time periods, for the CMIP6 FIO-ESM GCM, and forcing scenarios SSP245 (blue) and SSP585 (red), and locations on the meridional transect SoA. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is some evidence for increasing H_S in time, particularly at more southerly latitudes. Note that full name of CMIP6 GCM is FIO-ESM v2.0.

Figure SM4.32: Comparison of the ordered AM H_S for the Historical and Middle time periods, for the CMIP6 FIO-ESM GCM, and forcing scenarios SSP245 (blue) and SSP585 (red), and locations on the zonal transect SoA. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is some evidence for increasing H_S in time, particularly at more southerly latitudes. Note that full name of CMIP6 GCM is FIO-ESM v2.0.

Figure SM4.33: Comparison of the ordered AM H_S for the Historical and End time periods, for the CMIP6 FIO-ESM GCM, and forcing scenarios SSP245 (blue) and SSP585 (red), and locations on the meridional transect SoA. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is some evidence for increasing H_S in time. Note that full name of CMIP6 GCM is FIO-ESM v2.0.

Figure SM4.34: Comparison of the ordered AM H_S for the Historical and End time periods, for the CMIP6 FIO-ESM GCM, and forcing scenarios SSP245 (blue) and SSP585 (red), and locations on the zonal transect SoA. The line $y = x$ is added for guidance. There is some evidence for increasing H_S in time, especially for the RCP8.5 scenario. Note that full name of CMIP6 GCM is FIO-ESM v2.0.

Comparing ratios of ordered 40 largest values of POT H_S in different time periods at centre locations EoM and SoA, for all CMIP5 and CMIP6 GCMs

Figure SM4.35: Ratios of the ordered 40 largest values of POT H_S for different time periods, at the centre location EoM, for all CMIP5 and CMIP6 GCMs. Panels show ratios for the the Middle relative to Historical periods (left) and the End relative to Historical periods (right), for RCP4.5 (and SSP245, top) and RCP8.5 (and SSP585, bottom) forcing scenarios. The line $y = 1$ is added for guidance. There is general evidence for reducing H_S in time, but little for a trend with RCP.

Figure SM4.36: Ratios of the ordered 40 largest values of POT H_S for different time periods, at the centre location SoA, for all CMIP5 and CMIP6 GCMs. Panels show ratios for the the Middle relative to Historical periods (left) and the End relative to Historical periods (right), for RCP4.5 (top) and RCP8.5 (bottom) forcing scenarios. The line $y = 1$ is added for guidance. There is general evidence for increasing H_S in time, and some for a trend with RCP.

Comparing ratios of ordered AM H_S in different time periods at centre locations EoM and SoA, for all CMIP5 and CMIP6 GCMs

Figure SM4.37: Ratios of the ordered AM H_S for different time periods, at the centre location EoM, for all CMIP5 and CMIP6 GCMs. Panels show ratios for the the Middle relative to Historical periods (left) and the End relative to Historical periods (right), for RCP4.5 (top) and RCP8.5 (bottom) forcing scenarios. The line $y = 1$ is added for guidance. There is evidence for reducing H_S in time, but the inherent variability, and variability between GCMs in particular, is considerable. No evidence for a trend with RCP.

Figure SM4.38: Ratios of the ordered AM H_S for different time periods, at the centre location SoA, for all CMIP5 and CMIP6 GCMs. Panels show ratios for the the Middle relative to Historical periods (left) and the End relative to Historical periods (right), for RCP4.5 (top) and RCP8.5 (bottom) forcing scenarios. The line $y = 1$ is added for guidance. There is evidence for increasing H_S in time, but the inherent variability, and variability between GCMs in particular, is considerable.

Probability that the rate of POT H_S increases from Historical period, to Middle or End periods at centre point EoM and SoA, for all CMIP5 and CMIP6 GCMs and RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 forcing scenarios.

Figure SM4.39: Estimated probabilities that the ratio of rate of occurrence of POT H_S per annum increases in time, for centre location EoM (left) and centre location SoA (right), and forcing scenarios RCP4.5 (and SSP245, top) and RCP8.5 (and SSP585, bottom), for all CMIP5 and CMIP6 GCMs. There is general evidence for reduction in rate EoM, and increase in rate SoA.

SM5. Inherent steady state variability

Stationary Extremal Analysis of the piControl Data Set: Effect of segment length and threshold on temporal variability of 100-year return value estimate using POT H_S

Figure SM5.1: Estimates of 100-year H_S in time for the CMIP6 piControl data, using EV threshold NEP1. Each panel gives return value estimates from stationary EV analysis using an interval of data of “segment length” specified in panel title, starting at the year indicated on the x-axis, at the centre location EoM. Within each panel, the posterior median estimate is given as a blue line, and its 95% credible interval (CI) as a blue band. Also shown (in orange, and common to all panels) are the corresponding posterior median and 95% CI using the full 700 years of data for EV analysis. In each panel, the sample data is represented as black dots. The panel title also gives the value of non-exceedance probability τ corresponding to threshold level NEP1.

piControl GP, NEP 2: 14.59S, 56.19E

Figure SM5.2: Estimates of 100-year H_S in time for the CMIP6 piControl data, using EV threshold NEP2. Each panel gives return value estimates from stationary EV analysis using an interval of data of “segment length” specified in panel title, starting at the year indicated on the x-axis, at the centre location EoM. Within each panel, the posterior median estimate is given as a blue line, and its 95% credible interval (CI) as a blue band. Also shown (in orange, and common to all panels) are the corresponding posterior median and 95% CI using the full 700 years of data for EV analysis. In each panel, the sample data is represented as black dots. The panel title also gives the value of non-exceedance probability τ corresponding to threshold level NEP2.

piControl GP, NEP 3: 14.59S, 56.19E

Figure SM5.3: Estimates of 100-year H_S in time for the CMIP6 piControl data, using EV threshold NEP3. Each panel gives return value estimates from stationary EV analysis using an interval of data of “segment length” specified in panel title, starting at the year indicated on the x-axis, at the centre location EoM. Within each panel, the posterior median estimate is given as a blue line, and its 95% credible interval (CI) as a blue band. Also shown (in orange, and common to all panels) are the corresponding posterior median and 95% CI using the full 700 years of data for EV analysis. In each panel, the sample data is represented as black dots. The panel title also gives the value of non-exceedance probability τ corresponding to threshold level NEP3.

piControl GP, NEP 4: 14.59S, 56.19E

Figure SM5.4: Estimates of 100-year H_S in time for the CMIP6 piControl data, using EV threshold NEP4. Each panel gives return value estimates from stationary EV analysis using an interval of data of “segment length” specified in panel title, starting at the year indicated on the x-axis, at the centre location EoM. Within each panel, the posterior median estimate is given as a blue line, and its 95% credible interval (CI) as a blue band. Also shown (in orange, and common to all panels) are the corresponding posterior median and 95% CI using the full 700 years of data for EV analysis. In each panel, the sample data is represented as black dots. The panel title also gives the value of non-exceedance probability τ corresponding to threshold level NEP4.

piControl GP, NEP 1: 48.24S, 141.69E

Figure SM5.5: Estimates of 100-year H_S in time for the CMIP6 piControl data, using EV threshold NEP1. Each panel gives return value estimates from stationary EV analysis using an interval of data of “segment length” specified in panel title, starting at the year indicated on the x-axis, at the centre location SoA. Within each panel, the posterior median estimate is given as a blue line, and its 95% credible interval (CI) as a blue band. Also shown (in orange, and common to all panels) are the corresponding posterior median and 95% CI using the full 700 years of data for EV analysis. In each panel, the sample data is represented as black dots. The panel title also gives the value of non-exceedance probability τ corresponding to threshold level NEP1.

piControl GP, NEP 2: 48.24S, 141.69E

Figure SM5.6: Estimates of 100-year H_S in time for the CMIP6 piControl data, using EV threshold NEP2. Each panel gives return value estimates from stationary EV analysis using an interval of data of “segment length” specified in panel title, starting at the year indicated on the x-axis, at the centre location SoA. Within each panel, the posterior median estimate is given as a blue line, and its 95% credible interval (CI) as a blue band. Also shown (in orange, and common to all panels) are the corresponding posterior median and 95% CI using the full 700 years of data for EV analysis. In each panel, the sample data is represented as black dots. The panel title also gives the value of non-exceedance probability τ corresponding to threshold level NEP2.

piControl GP, NEP 3: 48.24S, 141.69E

Figure SM5.7: Estimates of 100-year H_S in time for the CMIP6 piControl data, using EV threshold NEP3. Each panel gives return value estimates from stationary EV analysis using an interval of data of “segment length” specified in panel title, starting at the year indicated on the x-axis, at the centre location SoA. Within each panel, the posterior median estimate is given as a blue line, and its 95% credible interval (CI) as a blue band. Also shown (in orange, and common to all panels) are the corresponding posterior median and 95% CI using the full 700 years of data for EV analysis. In each panel, the sample data is represented as black dots. The panel title also gives the value of non-exceedance probability τ corresponding to threshold level NEP3.

piControl GP, NEP 4: 48.24S, 141.69E

Figure SM5.8: Estimates of 100-year H_S in time for the CMIP6 piControl data, using EV threshold NEP4. Each panel gives return value estimates from stationary EV analysis using an interval of data of “segment length” specified in panel title, starting at the year indicated on the x-axis, at the centre location SoA. Within each panel, the posterior median estimate is given as a blue line, and its 95% credible interval (CI) as a blue band. Also shown (in orange, and common to all panels) are the corresponding posterior median and 95% CI using the full 700 years of data for EV analysis. In each panel, the sample data is represented as black dots. The panel title also gives the value of non-exceedance probability τ corresponding to threshold level NEP4.

Figure SM5.9: Illustration of posterior median fits of GP tails for peaks over threshold, using EV threshold non-exceedance probabilities NEP1-4 at the centre location EoM. Fits for NEP1 and NEP2 are poor. There is a “kink” in the empirical tail (blue) at around 6m, attributed to a mixed population of storms in the tail. Only EV thresholds exceeding this value will provide reasonable tail fits.

piControl 700-yr Segment GP SEVA Distributions - 48.24S, 141.69E

Figure SM5.10: Illustration of posterior median fits of GP tails for peaks over threshold, using EV threshold non-exceedance probabilities NEP1-4 at the centre location SoA. Fits for NEP2-4 are all reasonable.

piControl 700-yr Segment GEV SEVA Distributions - 14.59S, 56.19E

Figure SM5.11: Illustration of posterior median fits of GEV tails for block maxima events, using b -year block lengths with $b = 1, 5, 10$ and 20 at the centre location EoM. Annual maxima data shown in blue. Corresponding n -year block maxima shown as red circles. The fit for 1-year maxima (AM) is very poor. Blocks with length $n \geq 5$ provide reasonable tail fits.

piControl 700-yr Segment GEV SEVA Distributions - 48.24S, 141.69E

Figure SM5.12: Illustration of posterior median fits of GEV tails for block maxima events, using b -year block lengths with $b = 1, 5, 10$ and 20 at the centre location SoA. Annual maxima data shown in blue. Corresponding n -year block maxima shown as red circles. All block lengths provide reasonable tail fits.

Figure SM5.13: Estimates of 100-year H_S in time for 5-year maxima (5YM) from the CMIP6 piControl data for the centre location EoM (top) and SoA (bottom). Each panel gives return value estimates from stationary GEV using segment length specified in panel title: 100-years (left), 150 years (centre) and 165 years (right). Within each panel, the posterior median estimate is given as a blue line, and its 95% credible interval (CI) as a blue band. Also shown (in orange, and common to all panels) are the corresponding posterior median and 95% CI using the full 700 years of data for EV analysis. In each panel, the sample 5YM data is represented as black dots.

Zonal variability of 100-year return value as a function of threshold from POT H_S

Figure SM5.14: Estimates of zonal variation of 100-year POT H_S for EoM for the CMIP6 piControl data, using EV threshold levels NEP1-4. 13 pairs of ordered coloured lines in each panel give 95% credible intervals for the return value from stationary EV analysis using intervals of data of specific length. The calculation procedure is outlined in the text.

Figure SM5.15: Estimates of zonal variation of 100-year POT H_S for SoA for the CMIP6 piControl data, using EV threshold levels NEP1-4. 13 pairs of ordered coloured lines in each panel give 95% credible intervals for the return value from stationary EV analysis using intervals of data of specific length. The calculation procedure is outlined in the text.

Meridional variability of 100-year return value as a function of threshold from POT H_S

Figure SM5.16: Estimates of meridional variation of 100-year POT H_S for EoM for the CMIP6 piControl data, using EV threshold levels NEP1-4. 13 pairs of ordered coloured lines in each panel give 95% credible intervals for the return value from stationary EV analysis using intervals of data of specific length. The calculation procedure is outlined in the text.

Figure SM5.17: Estimates of meridional variation of 100-year POT H_S for SoA for the CMIP6 piControl data, using EV threshold levels NEP1-4. 13 pairs of ordered coloured lines in each panel give 95% credible intervals for the return value from stationary EV analysis using intervals of data of specific length. The calculation procedure is outlined in the text.

Figure SM5.18: Comparison of zonal variation of 100-year block maxima H_S for EoM (top) and SoA (bottom) for annual maxima (AM, left) and 5-year maxima (5YM, right) for the CMIP6 piControl data. 13 pairs of ordered coloured lines in each panel give 95% credible intervals for the return value from stationary EV analysis using intervals of data of specific length; only larger block lengths are possible for 5YM. The calculation procedure is outlined in the text.

Figure SM5.19: Comparison of meridional variation of 100-year block maxima H_S for EoM (top) and SoA (bottom) for annual maxima (AM, left) and 5-year maxima (5YM, right) for the CMIP6 piControl data. 13 pairs of ordered coloured lines in each panel give 95% credible intervals for the return value from stationary EV analysis using intervals of data of specific length; only larger block lengths are possible for 5YM. The calculation procedure is outlined in the text.

Effect of segment length on estimate of 100-year 5YM H_S for centre point locations

Figure SM5.20: Effect of segment length on estimate of 100-year return value for 5YM H_S at centre location East of Madagascar (left) and South of Australia (right). With respect to the left-hand y-axis, the dark and light orange bands refer respectively to (a) the 95% credible interval for the return value using the full sample, and (b) the empirical 95% uncertainty interval of *posterior median* return values for the segment length given on the x-axis. (The empirical estimate of uncertainty is obtained by reading off the 2.5 and 97.5 percentiles of the set of median return values over all starting years for a given segment length.) With respect to the right-hand y-axis, solid, dashed and dotted orange lines indicate the percentage of starting years for which (a) the estimated *posterior median* return value for given segment length lies outside the 95% credible interval estimated using the full sample, (b) the estimated *posterior median* return value using the full sample lies outside the 95% credible interval estimated using the given segment length, and (c) there is no overlap at all between 95% credible intervals estimated from the full sample and from a given segment length.

Figure SM5.21: Relative credible intervals for 100-year POT H_S at centre location EoM, for EV threshold levels NEP3 (left) and NEP4. Dots indicate the relative size of the 2.5% and 97.5% percentiles of the posterior distribution of return value to the median return value, for different segment lengths (colours) and start years, plotted against the posterior median return value. Thus there is only one possible dark red dot (corresponding to a segment length of 700 years, the length of the piControl time-series), whereas there are 680 (=700-20) dark blue dots (corresponding to segment length 20, and different starting years).

Figure SM5.22: Relative credible intervals for 100-year POT H_S at centre location EoM, for EV threshold levels NEP1-4. For other details, see Figure SM5.21.

Effect of segment length on credible intervals for 100-year 5YM H_S

Figure SM5.23: Relative credible intervals for 100-year 5YM H_S at centre location EoM (left) and SoA. For other details, see Figure SM5.21.

Figure SM5.24: Time evolution of 100-year POT H_S for locations EoM, using segments of length 86 years, the starting year of which is given on the x-axis (and the end year of which is 86 years later). In each panel, the blue band corresponds to the posterior 95% credible interval for 100-year POT H_S and the blue line to the median value for the start year. The corresponding red band and line summarise the posterior distribution of 100-year POT H_S at the end year.

Figure SM5.25: Time evolution of 100-year POT H_S for locations SoA, using segments of length 86 years, the starting year of which is given on the x-axis (and the end year of which is 86 years later). In each panel, the blue band corresponds to the posterior 95% credible interval for 100-year POT H_S and the blue line to the median value for the start year. The corresponding red band and line summarise the posterior distribution of 100-year POT H_S at the end year.

Figure SM5.26: Time evolution of 100-year POT H_S for locations EoM, using segments of length 122 years, the starting year of which is given on the x-axis (and the end year of which is 122 years later, noting “gaps” introduced to mimic structure of CMIP5 output; see Section 5 of main text). In each panel, the blue band corresponds to the posterior 95% credible interval for 100-year POT H_S and the blue line to the median value for the start year. The corresponding red band and line summarise the posterior distribution of 100-year POT H_S at the end year.

Figure SM5.27: Time evolution of 100-year POT H_S for locations SoA, using segments of length 122 years, the starting year of which is given on the x-axis (and the end year of which is 122 years later, noting “gaps” introduced to mimic structure of CMIP5 output; see Section 5 of main text). In each panel, the blue band corresponds to the posterior 95% credible interval for 100-year POT H_S and the blue line to the median value for the start year. The corresponding red band and line summarise the posterior distribution of 100-year POT H_S at the end year.

Figure SM5.28: Time evolution of 100-year POT H_S for locations EoM, using segments of length 150 years, the starting year of which is given on the x-axis (and the end year of which is 150 years later). In each panel, the blue band corresponds to the posterior 95% credible interval for 100-year POT H_S and the blue line to the median value for the start year. The corresponding red band and line summarise the posterior distribution of 100-year POT H_S at the end year.

Figure SM5.29: Time evolution of 100-year POT H_S for locations SoA, using segments of length 150 years, the starting year of which is given on the x-axis (and the end year of which is 150 years later). In each panel, the blue band corresponds to the posterior 95% credible interval for 100-year POT H_S and the blue line to the median value for the start year. The corresponding red band and line summarise the posterior distribution of 100-year POT H_S at the end year.

Figure SM5.30: Time evolution of 100-year POT H_S for locations EoM, using segments of length 165 years, the starting year of which is given on the x-axis (and the end year of which is 165 years later). In each panel, the blue band corresponds to the posterior 95% credible interval for 100-year POT H_S and the blue line to the median value for the start year. The corresponding red band and line summarise the posterior distribution of 100-year POT H_S at the end year.

Figure SM5.31: Time evolution of 100-year POT H_S for locations SoA, using segments of length 165 years, the starting year of which is given on the x-axis (and the end year of which is 165 years later). In each panel, the blue band corresponds to the posterior 95% credible interval for 100-year POT H_S and the blue line to the median value for the start year. The corresponding red band and line summarise the posterior distribution of 100-year POT H_S at the end year.

Effect of segment length on 100-year POT H_S from non-stationary EV analysis

Figure SM5.32: Density of median 100-year POT H_S for locations EoM, corresponding to start and end years 86 years apart, using segments of length 86 years.

Figure SM5.33: Density of median 100-year POT H_S for locations SoA, corresponding to start and end years 86 years apart, using segments of length 86 years.

Figure SM5.34: Density of median 100-year POT H_S for locations EoM, corresponding to start and end years 122 years apart, using segments of length 122 years.

Figure SM5.35: Density of median 100-year POT H_S for locations SoA, corresponding to start and end years 122 years apart, using segments of length 122 years.

Figure SM5.36: Density of median 100-year POT H_S for locations EoM, corresponding to start and end years 150 years apart, using segments of length 150 years.

Figure SM5.37: Density of median 100-year POT H_S for locations SoA, corresponding to start and end years 150 years apart, using segments of length 150 years.

Figure SM5.38: Density of median 100-year POT H_S for locations EoM, corresponding to start and end years 165 years apart, using segments of length 165 years.

Figure SM5.39: Density of median 100-year POT H_S for locations SoA, corresponding to start and end years 165 years apart, using segments of length 165 years.

Effect of segment length on change in 100-year POT H_S from non-stationary EV analysis

Figure SM5.40: Density of median difference in 100-year POT H_S between start and end years 86 years apart, for locations EoM, using segments of length 86 years.

Figure SM5.41: Density of median difference in 100-year POT H_S between start and end years 86 years apart, for locations SoA, using segments of length 86 years.

Figure SM5.42: Density of median difference in 100-year POT H_S between start and end years 122 years apart, for locations EoM, using segments of length 122 years.

Figure SM5.43: Density of median difference in 100-year POT H_S between start and end years 122 years apart, for locations SoA, using segments of length 122 years.

Figure SM5.44: Density of median difference in 100-year POT H_S between start and end years 150 years apart, for locations EoM, using segments of length 150 years.

Figure SM5.45: Density of median difference in 100-year POT H_S between start and end years 150 years apart, for locations SoA, using segments of length 150 years.

Figure SM5.46: Density of median difference in 100-year POT H_S between start and end years 165 years apart, for locations EoM, using segments of length 165 years.

Figure SM5.47: Density of median difference in 100-year POT H_S between start and end years 165 years apart, for locations SoA, using segments of length 165 years.

SM6. Temporal trends

Probability of an increase in 100-year POT H_S for CMIP5 and CMIP6 output

Figure SM6.1: Probability of increased return value: Meridional transect, EoM, RCP4.5 (and SSP245). Each panel gives estimated probability that 100-year POT H_S increases over the period of study, for EV thresholds NEP3 (dash-dot) and NEP4 (dot). Grey lines are empirical 2.5% and 97.5% uncertainty bands compiled from the analysis of 200 time-permuted POT data sets. Coloured dots indicate any locations at which the coloured line crosses the corresponding grey line, which can be viewed as evidence of a significant trend. First 7 panels give results for individual CMIP5 GCMs, and final panel for the CMIP6 GCM.

Figure SM6.2: Probability of increased return value: POT, zonal transect, EoM, RCP4.5. For details, see Figure SM6.1.

Figure SM6.3: Probability of increased return value: POT, meridional transect, EoM, RCP8.5 (and SSP585). For details, see Figure SM6.1.

Figure SM6.4: Probability of increased return value: POT, zonal transect, EoM, RCP8.5. For details, see Figure SM6.1.

Figure SM6.5: Probability of increased return value: Meridional transect, SoA, RCP4.5. Each panel gives estimated probability that 100-year POT H_5 increases over the period of study, for EV thresholds NEP1 (solid), NEP2 (dashed), NEP3 (dash-dot) and NEP4 (dot). First 7 panels give results for individual CMIP5 GCMs, and final panel for the CMIP6 GCM.

Figure SM6.6: Probability of increased return value: POT, zonal transect, SoA, RCP4.5. For details, see Figure SM6.5.

Figure SM6.7: Probability of increased return value: POT, meridional transect, SoA, RCP8.5. For details, see Figure SM6.5.

Figure SM6.8: Probability of increased return value: POT, zonal transect, SoA, RCP8.5. For details, see Figure SM6.5.

Probability of an increase in 100-year AM H_S for CMIP5 output

Figure SM6.9: Probability of increased return value: Meridional transect, EoM, RCP4.5 (and SSP245). Each panel gives estimated probability that 100-year AM H_S using increases over the period of study. Grey lines are empirical 2.5% and 97.5% uncertainty bands compiled from the analysis of 200 time-permuted POT data sets. Coloured dots indicate any locations at which the coloured line crosses the corresponding grey line. First 7 panels give results for individual CMIP5 GCMs, and final panel for CMIP6. Note that these results are based on AM data (not 5YM); this is necessary because the number of years of data is small especially for CMIP5, and analysis of a very small sample of 5YM data is unwise. These AM results should therefore be treated with caution for EoM.

Figure SM6.10: Probability of increased return value: AM, meridional transect, EoM, RCP8.5 (and SSP585). For details, see Figure SM6.9.

Figure SM6.11: Probability of increased return value: AM, zonal transect, EoM, RCP4.5. For details, see Figure SM6.9.

Figure SM6.12: Probability of increased return value: AM, zonal transect, EoM, RCP8.5. For details, see Figure SM6.9.

Figure SM6.13: Probability of increased return value: AM, meridional transect, SoA, RCP4.5. For details, see Figure SM6.9.

Figure SM6.14: Probability of increased return value: AM, meridional transect, SoA, RCP8.5. For details, see Figure SM6.9.

Figure SM6.15: Probability of increased return value: AM, zonal transect, SoA, RCP4.5. For details, see Figure SM6.9.

Figure SM6.16: Probability of increased return value: AM, zonal transect, SoA, RCP8.5. For details, see Figure SM6.9.

Figure SM6.17: Estimated change in 100-year POT H_S for climate scenario RCP4.5 (and SSP245) for the meridional transect EoM. The 8 panels show estimates for 7 CMIP5 and CMIP6 GCMs. In each panel, coloured lines are posterior median differences in 100-year POT H_S return value from the MCMC, for non-exceedance thresholds levels NEP3 (dash-dot) and NEP4 (dot). Grey lines are empirical 2.5% and 97.5% uncertainty bands for the median difference in return value estimates compiled from the analysis of 200 time-permuted POT data sets. Informally, if a coloured line lies outside the corresponding uncertainty band, we are “surprised” by the extent of temporal trend observed. In this figure, therefore, none of the locations exhibit “significant” time trends. The “time-permuted” uncertainty bands are expected to be symmetric about “ $y = 0$ ”. Note that the time period for CMIP5 GCMs is 122 years; panels illustrate the change in 100-year POT H_S over 122 years, estimated from an extreme value model fitted to a sample spanning 122 years. For CMIP6, with data period 86 years, the final panel illustrates the change in 100-year POT H_S over 86 years, estimated from an extreme value model fitted to a sample corresponding to 86 years. Note further that, for the summary of trends given in Figure 14 of the main text, we quantify the change in 100-year POT H_S over 122 years for both CMIP5 and CMIP6, requiring extrapolation in time for the CMIP6 EV model.

Figure SM6.18: Estimated change in 100-year POT H_S , meridional transect, EoM, RCP8.5 (and SSP585). For details, see Figure SM6.17. There is evidence for a decreasing trend in return value with time for e.g. MIROC5 GCM. It is striking that estimates for “time-permuted” uncertainty for some GCMs is considerably larger than for others.

Figure SM6.19: Estimated change in 100-year POT H_S , zonal transect, EoM, RCP4.5. For details, see Figure SM6.17. There is little evidence for a changing return value.

Figure SM6.20: Estimated change in 100-year POT H_S , zonal transect, EoM, RCP8.5. For details, see Figure SM6.17. There is evidence for a decreasing trend in return value with time for e.g. MIROC5 GCM. It is again striking that estimates for “time-permuted” uncertainty for some GCMs is considerably larger than for others.

Figure SM6.21: Estimated change in 100-year POT H_S for climate scenario RCP4.5 for the meridional transect SoA. The 8 panels show estimates for 7 CMIP5 and CMIP6 GCMs. In each panel, coloured lines are posterior median differences in 100-year POT H_S return value from the MCMC, for non-exceedance thresholds levels NEP1 (solid), NEP2 (dash), NEP3 (dash-dot) and NEP4 (dot). Grey lines are empirical 2.5% and 97.5% uncertainty bands for the median difference in return value estimates compiled from the analysis of 200 time-permuted POT data sets. Coloured dots indicate any locations at which the coloured line crosses the corresponding grey line. Informally, if a coloured line lies outside the corresponding uncertainty band, we are “surprised” by the extent of temporal trend observed. In this figure, there is conflicting evidence from different GCMs, but in general more evidence for an increasing trend in return value.

Figure SM6.22: Estimated change in 100-year POT H_S , meridional transect, SoA, RCP8.5. For details, see Figure SM6.17. There is evidence for an increasing trend in return value from a number of GCMs.

Figure SM6.23: Estimated change in 100-year POT H_S , zonal transect, SoA, RCP4.5. For details, see Figure SM6.17. There is conflicting evidence across GCMs.

Figure SM6.24: Estimated change in 100-year POT H_S , zonal transect, SoA, RCP8.5. For details, see Figure SM6.17. There is evidence for an increasing trend in return value from a number of GCMs.

Probability of an increase in 100-year POT H_S for CMIP6 POT output

Figure SM6.25: Probability of increased return value in CMIP6 output: meridional transect, EoM. Panels give estimated probability that 100-year POT H_S using increases over the period of study, for non-exceedance thresholds levels NEP3 (dash-dot) and NEP4 (dot) for each of the 7 climate scenarios (piControl, Historical, SSP126, SSP245, SSP585, 1pctCO2, Abrupt-4xCO2). Grey lines are empirical 2.5% and 97.5% uncertainty bands for the median difference in return value estimates compiled from the analysis of 200 time-permuted POT data sets. Coloured dots indicate any locations at which the coloured line crosses the corresponding grey line.

Figure SM6.26: Probability of increased return value in CMIP6 output: POT, zonal transect, EoM. For other details, see Figure SM6.25.

Figure SM6.27: Probability of increased return value in CMIP6 output: meridional transect, SoA. Panels give estimated probability that 100-year POT H_S increases over the period of study, for non-exceedance thresholds levels NEP1 (solid), NEP2 (dash), NEP3 (dash-dot) and NEP4 (dot) for each of the 7 climate scenarios (piControl, Historical, SSP126, SSP245, SSP585, 1pctCO2, Abrupt-4xCO2). Grey lines are empirical 2.5% and 97.5% uncertainty bands for the median difference in return value estimates compiled from the analysis of 200 time-permuted POT data sets. Coloured dots indicate any locations at which the coloured line crosses the corresponding grey line.

Figure SM6.28: Probability of increased return value in CMIP6 output: POT, zonal transect, SoA. For other details, see Figure SM6.27.

Probability of an increase in 100-year POT H_S for CMIP6 AM output

Figure SM6.29: Probability of increased return value in CMIP6 output: meridional transect, EoM. Panels give estimated probability that 100-year AM H_S increases over the period of study for each of the 7 climate scenarios (piControl, Historical, SSP126, SSP245, SSP585, 1pctCO2, Abrupt-4xCO2). Grey lines are empirical 2.5% and 97.5% uncertainty bands for the median difference in return value estimates compiled from the analysis of 200 time-permuted POT data sets. Coloured dots indicate any locations at which the coloured line crosses the grey line. Note that, because of limited sample length, results for AM (rather than 5YM) are reported here.

Figure SM6.30: Probability of increased return value in CMIP6 output: 5YM, zonal transect, EoM. For other details, see Figure SM6.29.

Figure SM6.31: Probability of increased return value in CMIP6 output: 5YM, meridional transect, SoA. For other details, see Figure SM6.29.

Figure SM6.32: Probability of increased return value in CMIP6 output: 5YM, zonal transect, SoA. For other details, see Figure SM6.29.

Figure SM6.33: Mean (over estimates using EV thresholds NEP3-4) of the posterior median 100-year POT H_S return value for the meridional transect EoM and the RCP4.5 (and SSP245) scenario. Panels show estimates for the 7 CMIP5 and CMIP6 GCM output at the start time (solid) and the end time (dashed). Note that the time period for CMIP5 GCMs is 122 years; panels illustrate 100-year POT H_S for 1979 (start) and 2100 (end), estimated from an extreme value model fitted to a sample spanning 122 years. For CMIP6, with data period 86 years, the final panel illustrates 100-year POT H_S for 2015 (start) and 2100 (end), estimated from an extreme value model fitted to a sample corresponding to 86 years. Note further that, for the summary of trends given in Figure 14 of the main text, we quantify the change in 100-year POT H_S over 122 years for both CMIP5 and CMIP6, requiring extrapolation in time for the CMIP6 EV model.

Figure SM6.34: Mean (over estimates using EV thresholds NEP3-4) of the posterior median 100-year POT H_S return value for the meridional transect EoM and the RCP8.5 (and SSP485) scenario. For other details, see Figure SM6.33.

Figure SM6.35: Mean (over estimates using EV thresholds NEP3-4) of the posterior median 100-year POT H_S return value for the zonal transect EoM and the RCP4.5 scenario. For other details, see Figure SM6.33.

Figure SM6.36: Mean (over estimates using EV thresholds NEP3-4) of the posterior median 100-year POT H_S return value for the zonal transect EoM and the RCP8.5 scenario. For other details, see Figure SM6.33.

Figure SM6.37: Mean (over estimates using EV thresholds NEP1-4) of the posterior median 100-year POT H_S return value for the meridional transect SoA and the RCP4.5 scenario. For other details, see Figure SM6.33.

Figure SM6.38: Mean (over estimates using EV thresholds NEP1-4) of the posterior median 100-year POT H_S return value for the meridional transect SoA and the RCP8.5 scenario. For other details, see Figure SM6.33.

Figure SM6.39: Mean (over estimates using EV thresholds NEP1-4) of the posterior median 100-year POT H_S return value for the zonal transect SoA and the RCP4.5 scenario. For other details, see Figure SM6.33.

Figure SM6.40: Mean (over estimates using EV thresholds NEP1-4) of the posterior median 100-year POT H_s return value for the zonal transect SoA and the RCP8.5 scenario. For other details, see Figure SM6.33.

Figure SM6.41: Comparison of best estimates for the 100-year POT H_S at the start and end years EoM and the RCP4.5 (and SSP245) scenario. Figure shows means (over estimates using thresholds NEP3-4) of the posterior median 100-year POT H_S return value for all CMIP5 and CMIP6 GCMs (coloured lines) and their grand mean (black dash) for start year (left) and end year (right), and meridional (top) and zonal (bottom) transects. Note that the time period for CMIP5 GCMs is 122 years; panels illustrate 100-year POT H_S for 1979 (start) and 2100 (end), estimated from an extreme value model fitted to a sample spanning 122 years. For CMIP6, with data period 86 years, the panels illustrate 100-year POT H_S for 2015 (start) and 2100 (end), estimated from an extreme value model fitted to a sample corresponding to 86 years. Note further that, for the summary of trends given in Figure 14 of the main text, we quantify the change in 100-year POT H_S over 122 years for both CMIP5 and CMIP6, requiring extrapolation in time for the CMIP6 EV model.

Figure SM6.42: Comparison of best estimates for the 100-year POT H_s at the start and end years EoM and the RCP8.5 (and SSP585) scenario. For other details, see Figure SM6.41.

Figure SM6.43: Comparison of best estimates for the 100-year POT H_S at the start and end years SoA and the RCP4.5 scenario. Figure shows means (over estimates using thresholds NEP1-4) of the posterior median 100-year POT H_S return value for all CMIP5 and CMIP6 GCMs (coloured lines) and their grand mean (black dash) for start year (left) and end year (right), and meridional (top) and zonal (bottom) transects. For other details, see Figure SM6.41.

Figure SM6.44: Comparison of best estimates for the 100-year POT H_S at the start and end years SoA and the RCP8.5 scenario. For other details, see Figure SM6.41.

SM7. Discussion and conclusions

There are no supporting figures for this section.

SMA. Bayesian inference

There are no supporting figures for this section.

SMB. Propagation of generalised Pareto threshold uncertainty

Figure SMB.1: Illustration of posterior densities for the distribution of the 100-year return value for storm peak H_S estimated under different assumptions regarding propagation of EV threshold uncertainty. Panels represent different choices. The first three labelled densities (solid lines) correspond to the density of the 100-year maximum estimated for the starting year, the last three labelled densities (dashed lines) to the end year. Colour indicates the choice made regarding threshold uncertainty propagation: (a) independent draws of $\hat{\psi}^S$ and $\hat{\psi}^E$ from their posterior marginal distributions, (b) common draw of $(\hat{\psi}^S, \hat{\psi}^E)$ from its posterior joint distribution, (c) use of posterior mean values of $\hat{\psi}^S$ and $\hat{\psi}^E$.